

Fintech Innovation and Banking Stability: Evidence from a Developing Country

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Abstract

Background: Technology has created many new financial services to help banks improve their competitiveness in customer service. Does technological innovation increase instability for banks? In addition, do we consider whether the impact of fintech innovation (FI) on banking stability (BS) varies with scale?

Objective: This study aimed to examine the role of Fintech Innovation (FI) in Banking Stability (BS) using quantile regression in a developing country.

Method: This study used the quantile regression method with a focus from 2012–2022. The quantile regression method is less sensitive to outliers, skewed distributions, and heterogeneity of the dependent variable. The results were presented in tables and charts for visual illustration.

Result: First, FI impacts BS negatively, and there are differences in this relationship across groups of banks with different capital sizes. This impact is also negative in the group of banks with large capital size, but it is not statistically significant for the groups of banks with low capital size. Second, the relationship between FI and different distributions of BS is different.

Conclusion: The relationship between FI and BS is different between different distributions of BS. This shows that if FI is not suitable, it can increase the instability of banking activities according to each bank's stability levels.

Unique contribution: The study provides empirical evidence on the trend of FI impact on BS in developing countries.

Key recommendation: The study proposes important policy implications for regulators in designing bank-specific strategies for technological development in the context of digitalization.

Keywords: Fintech Innovation-FI, Banking Stability-BS, Quantile Regression

Introduction

The literature related to FI largely focuses on aspects that increase competitive advantage for banks, changes the bank's profits and credit risk tolerance (Chen et al., 2023). Studies related to FI and BS have been conducted in the past, but the results have not been consistent. Fung et al. (2020) found that FI increases BS in emerging financial markets, but increases financial institution instability in developed financial markets. However, they only use data based on the number of FinTech companies in the market. Similarly, Daud et al. (2022) found that

FinTech promotes financial stability through multiple channels such as cloud technology, artificial intelligence, and data technology. Meanwhile, Vučinić (2020) has the exact opposite result and claims that the development of FinTech increases potential risks to the financial system. Therefore, the impact of FI development on BS may not be uniform and may differ between developed and developing countries. Therefore, do banks in emerging markets need to review their investment levels to adjust to increasing FI to maintain stability?

Unlike previous studies, this study clarifies the fundamental differences between Fintech and FI in banking operations. Some studies based on internal financial technology index of the bank such as total cost for technology and technology input (Wang et al., 2023); mining index from bank annual report (Chen et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023). Some use FI metrics from external banking metrics including digital transformation metrics (Chen et al., 2023); financial blockchain (Wang et al., 2023); comprehensive financial index (Hu et al., 2024).

The profitability performance of Vietnamese banks plays an important role in influencing the stability of global banks. Besides, the bank is the dominant part of the financial system in Vietnam (Nguyen & Dang, 2023). To the author's knowledge, there are very few studies analysing the impact of FI on BS due to the lack of data on technological innovation. Therefore, this study aims to fill the gap by approaching FI adaptability in emerging markets; this study uses a dataset measuring FI adaptability from 26 commercial banks in Vietnam from 2012–2022 by applying the quantile regression method. In addition, do we consider whether the impact of FI on BS varies with scale?

Theoretical basis and development of hypotheses

Currently, studies have begun to analyse digital transformation from a Fintech perspective. “Fintech” is a combination of financial and technological factors. Fintech focuses primarily on product enhancement in the financial industry, and technological innovation covers every aspect of the organisation, from structure to customer service. For example, Cheng and Qu (2020) explored the impact of banking Fintech products on credit risk based on banks' annual reports.

In the banking industry, FI can be considered a challenge (Fung et al., 2020) after introducing traditional IT hardware and software. In the next stage, banks developed internet finance (Zhao et al., 2022). However, Fintech products have recently been developed for lending and capital activities (Lee et al., 2021). Chen et al. (2023) argue that FI can improve bank performance. These studies can be classified into external and internal impacts. Internal impact, FinTech helps optimise credit allocation or control loans and increase efficiency in loan processing (Lee et al., 2021). External impact: FinTech accelerates decision-making related to business processes and improves financial performance.

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The author found that most of the literature related to FI and BS is divided into two perspectives. *Based on the “asymmetric information” theory, the view holds that FI improves BS.* Based on this theory, it is assumed that asymmetric information can positively affect the stock market. With the advantage of collecting and analysing big data, FI will be the solution to increase transparency and can increase BS (Lee et al., 2021). Fung et al. (2020) argue that FI can reduce volatility through increased diversification, information transparency and facilitation of financial services.

Meanwhile, the “Competition and Stability” hypothesis suggests that increased market competition will reduce the quality of loans, increasing the instability of banking operations.

Most studies suggest that FI increases the competitiveness of banks (Ding et al., 2022). However, in a context of increased competition, banks will be more vulnerable if they fall into financial difficulties (Wu et al., 2023). This study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1. There is a negative relationship between FI and BS in emerging markets.

Data and research methods

Research data

The research data includes 25 commercial banks in the period 2012 - 2022, collected from audited financial reports according to Vietnamese accounting standards. FI indicators are collected from reports of the Ministry of Information and Communications of Vietnam¹ and macro variables are collected from the World Bank's electronic information portal (www.worldbank.org). After filtering the data, the sample accounts for 80% of the system's banks.

Research variables

Dependent variable

Financial stability in banking operations is understood as the state of the financial system performing its functions effectively and being able to withstand economic shocks. There are many methods to measure BS. This study is based on using the mean and estimating the standard deviation of the return rate over the entire sample period (Čihák & Hesse, 2010). The larger the z-score, the higher the stability (Vučinić, 2020). The study also utilises RAROA, reflecting the risk-adjusted return on assets (Köhler, 2015), ROE according to previous documents (Köhler, 2015) to measure BS. This indicator aims to see whether the increase (or decrease) in overall financial stability stems from asset risk reduction or capital increase. A comprehensive view of operational effectiveness and financial risk in the banking sector helps to evaluate more accurately the stability of the bank.

Independent variables

Currently, there is no official FI index developed by the regulatory agencies and there is no unified conclusion on the FI measurement index (Daud et al., 2022). Many studies have used this index in Vietnam (Ngo & Le, 2022) to assess the impact of FI on BS in Vietnam. The ICT Index is a compilation of four standardized component indicators: (1) technology infrastructure, (2) human resource infrastructure, (3) internal banking application and (4) online banking services.

In addition, the study proposes to use the variable *IT*- natural base log of total investment in technology of bank *i* at time *t*, according to the approach (Beccalli, 2007). Data from the financial statement notes (excluding land use rights, copyrights, and patents) are collected from the new purchase cost and investment in intangible fixed assets during the year. Variable representing the characteristics of the bank under consideration according to the CAMELS early warning model, according to Chen et al. (2023), includes *L_A*, *SIZE*, *ASSET_GRO* and the macro factors are GDP growth rate and inflation rate (Chen et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023).

Research model

The study uses the method of quantile regression proposed by Koenker & Bassett Jr. (to estimate the parameters of the regression function on each quantile of the dependent variable.

¹ <https://mic.gov.vn/solieubaocao/Pages/TinTuc/143252/Bao-cao-Vietnam-ICT-Index.html>

The percentile regression equation is as follows:

$$y = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)x_1 + \dots + \beta_k(\tau)x_k + u(\tau) \quad (1)$$

In there:

$Q(y | x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)$ represents the conditional quantile of the dependent variable Y according to the independent variables x .

$\beta_0(\tau), \beta_1(\tau), \beta_2(\tau), \dots, \beta_p(\tau)$ are the regression coefficients of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k , at a given τ percentile.

With research hypotheses, research models evaluate the impact of **FI** and **BS**, the case in Vietnam is proposed to be built as follows:

$$Q(Y_{i,t} | X_{i,t}) = PSi,t = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau) FI_{i,t} + \beta_2(\tau) IT_{i,t} + \beta_3(\tau) BankChar_{i,t} + \beta_4(\tau) Macrot + \epsilon_{i,t}(\tau) \quad (2)$$

In this expression, $Q(Y_{i,t} | X_{i,t})$ is the quantile regression function; the dependent variable PSi,t measures the stability of the bank; $FI_{i,t}$ and $IT_{i,t}$ is the bank's technology innovation index. $BankChar_{i,t}$ The bank-specific coefficient of bank i in year t (such as L_A ; $SIZE$, $ASSET_GRO$) and the macroeconomic factors of year t (GDP , INF). Variable β is the regression coefficient and ϵ_{it} is the characteristic error, which can be called the unobserved residual of bank i at time t . The subscripts i and t denote the i -th bank in year t . $(0,1)$ is the quantile chosen to perform the regression. However, quantile regression can be performed with any quantile in the interval $(0,1)$. However, the article only presents regression results on quantiles $0.10 - 0.25 - 0.5 - 0.75 - 0.90$, commonly used in empirical studies test.

Estimation method

Quantile regression method is used for the following 3 reasons: *Firstly*, this method provides a detailed representation of the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables across different segments of the dependent variable, rather than just analyzing the impact at the average value of bank stability, as previous studies have done. *Secondly*, the quantile regression method is less sensitive to outliers, skewed distribution, and inhomogeneity of the dependent variable (Kannadhasan & Das, 2020). *Thirdly*, the statistical significance tests of the regression coefficient quantiles do not rely on the normality of the error; nor do they depend on any assumption about the distribution form of the regression error (Lin & Xu, 2018). *Fourthly*, quantile regression also helps verify the asymmetry in the impact of the studied factors on **BS**; specifically, the impact at different quantiles of banking stability will be different, which other studies with other regression methods cannot show (Lin & Xu, 2018). The study estimated the coefficients at the common percentiles of 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th percentiles.

Analysis of research results

4.1 Descriptive statistics and correlations between variables

Table 2 presents statistical data of variables used in the model, with the average values (min, max) of Z-scores being 14.182 (2.322, 65.117), similar to samples in previous studies (Nguyen & Dang, 2023). **Table 3** shows that the variables Z , ROE , and $RAROA$ change from low to high from the 25th and 90th percentiles. The IT index is 0.252; 0.811, respectively, and the average value is 0.623, showing that Vietnam's level of technological development is not high compared to developed countries. **Table 3** shows that there is no possibility of serious multicollinearity in the model because the correlation coefficients between the variables are quite small (VIF average is 3.45, lower than the usual threshold of 10)

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	Min	Q.25	Q.50	Q.75	Q.90	Max
ROE	275	0.085	0.067	0.000	0.041	0.082	0.142	0.200	0.263
RAROA	275	0.008	0.006	0.000	0.003	0.006	0.010	0.018	0.032

ZSCORE	275	14.182	3.036	2.322	3.495	4.029	4.627	5.467	65.117
IT	275	0.486	0.122	0.191	0.400	0.484	0.575	0.649	0.856
ICT	275	0.623	0.116	0.252	0.457	0.512	0.576	0.697	0.811
ASSET_GRO	275	0.145	0.134	-0.367	0.081	0.140	0.199	0.286	0.797
SIZE	275	18.990	1.138	16.588	18.244	18.92	19.842	20.58	21.475
L_A	275	0.595	0.115	0.222	0.532	0.604	0.678	0.722	0.972
GDP_GRO	275	0.056	0.014	0.025	0.050	0.062	0.068	0.070	0.070
INF	275	0.037	0.022	0.006	0.027	0.03	0.041	0.066	0.091

Note: The main variables includes BS indicators (RAROA, ROE, ZSCORE) as dependent variables. The independent variables include IT, ICT representing the new technology transformation variable. The bank-specific variables include Size; L_A; ASSET_GRO. The macro variables include GDP and INF.

Table 3: Correlation table between variables

	ROE	RAROA	Z_SCORE	IT	ICT	INF	GDP	ASSET_GRO	SIZE	VIF
ROE	1									
RAROA	0.064	1								
Z_SCORE	-0.032	-0.263	1							
IT	0.323	0.281	-0.055	1						
ICT	0.171	0.126	0.049	0.579	1					
INF	-0.134	-0.062	-0.165	-0.062	-0.013	1				
GDP	-0.155	-0.174	0.146	-0.277	-0.165	-0.068	1			
ASSET_GRO	0.182	0.119	-0.099	0.039	0.119	-0.115	-0.115	1		
SIZE	0.511	0.297	0.028	0.268	0.209	-0.226	0.1	0.034	1	
L_A	0.360	0.210	-0.109	0.215	0.103	0.303	-0.007	0.023	0.415	3.45

Note: The dependent variables include as the indicators RAROA, ROE, ZSCORE which represent BS variable. The independent variables include as IT, ICT which represent FI variable. The control variables representing the bank characteristics include SIZE; L_A; ASSET_GRO. The macro variables include GDP and INF.

Results and regression analysis

Analysis of results by the quantile regression method

In Table 4, the results of QR show that the ICT coefficient has a negative impact on BS(ROE) at the 75th percentile and decreases at the 90th percentile, statistically insignificant at the 25th and 50th percentiles. Similarly, the ICT coefficient has a negative impact on BS (RAROA) at the 75th percentile and gradually at the 90th percentile, statistically insignificant at the 25th and 50th percentiles. This ICT index hurts BS (ZCORE) at the 75th percentile and is statistically insignificant at the 25th, 50th, and 90th percentiles.

The regression coefficients are negative and significant, implying that FI will negatively affect BS in emerging market countries. Similar to the results of (Fung et al., 2020), the development of FI affects BS, depending on the different financial systems of each country. However, this viewpoint contradicts the results of (Daud et al., 2022), arguing that (FI) generally increases (BS) and (Cheng & Qu, 2020), arguing that (FI) reduces the risk to banks due to the features of new technology. Overall, the results in Table 4 are consistent with the expectation of hypothesis H1, i.e., an increase in FI reduces BS in emerging markets. The heterogeneity shows the complexity between BS and FI, which shows the importance of a clearer and more intuitive understanding of this relationship. Similarly, the ICT coefficient has a negative impact on BS (RAROA) at the 75th and 90th percentiles and is not statistically significant at lower percentiles. Next, the author conducts a test of the impact of FI on BS that differs between groups of banks of different sizes (see table 5). For the group of large banks, FI has a negative impact on BS (ROE) at the 75th and 90th percentiles, not statistically significant at the 25th and 50th percentiles. Similarly, the ICT coefficient has a negative impact on BS (RAROA) at the 75th, 90th percentiles and is statistically insignificant at the 25th, 50th percentiles. However, this ICT factor has a negative impact on BS (ZCORE) at the 25-50 percentile and is not statistically significant for the 75-90 percentile. For the group of small banks, there is no evidence to prove this relationship between FI and BS, except that the IT indicators measuring FI have a positive impact on BS (ROE, RAROA), which are all at the 90th percentile and have no statistical significance at the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles. The research results are similar to the results of (Cheng & Qu, 2020), which suggests that banks applying the system will take advantage of many modern features and thereby help increase revenue and improve banking operations.

The study plots the coefficients of the bank capital variable on the vertical axis and the quantiles on the horizontal axis. The regression coefficients of the FI variables are positive at lower quantiles and turn negative at higher quantiles (Figure 1). The majority of the regression coefficients of the ICT variables are negative. The majority of the regression coefficients of the ICT variables are negative. The coefficients are lower than the OLS estimates for some quantiles and higher for others. The impact of FI is not uniform across the entire distribution of BS. Therefore, QR provides a more complete picture of the relationship between FI and BS (see Figures 2, 3).

TABLE 4: FI AND BS: USING THE QUANTILE REGRESSION METHOD

BẢNG A: FULLBANK

	ROE				RAROA				Z-CORE			
	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90
ICT	0.032	-0.020	- 0.052**	- 0.174*	-0.001	-0.001	- 0.002**	-0.006**	1.833	1.358	-0.189*	-0.215
IT	0.056	0.083	0.104	0.088	0.007	0.00**	0.006	0.03***	-0.430	- 0.951*	-0.516	-0.723
L_A	0.120***	0.100***	0.053	0.162	0.007* **	0.008**	0.011	-0.003	-0.197	- 1.505* *	- 1.960** *	- 3.747**
SIZE	0.01***	0.02***	0.03***	0.04** *	0.00**	0.001	0.00**	0.004***	0.014	0.084	0.073	0.23**
ASSET_GRO	0.04*	0.08**	0.105**	0.160* **	0.001	0.006	0.005	0.002	-1.04*	- 1.24** *	-0.808	-0.501
GDP_GRO	-0.227	-0.401	-0.337	-0.204	-0.028	-0.051	-0.094	-0.015	4.278	7.042	6.292	20.42** *
INF	0.240	0.133	0.210	0.266	0.016	0.03*	0.039	0.072	-5.126	- 8.97** *	- 11.6***	-13.151
Cons	-0.411	-0.412	-0.534	-0.685	-0.011	-0.013	-0.041	-0.071	2.743	3.291	5.012	3.014
No.obs	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275
Pseudo R2	0.203	0.241	0.241	0.238	0.109	0.080	0.116	0.171	0.028	0.062	0.086	0.138

Note: This table presents the result of estimating Equation (1) using the quantile regression method.

Q25, Q50, Q75 and Q90 are the 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th quantiles respectively. ***p < 0,01; **p < 0,05; * p < 0,1.

Figure 1. Quantile regression processes – Fullbank with 25 Bank

Source(s): Author’s own creation/work

Note: This table presents the result of estimating Equation (1) using the quantile regression method.

Figure 2. Quantile regression processes – Smallbank

Figure 3. Quantile regression processes – Largebank

Source(s): Author's own creation/work

TABLE 5: FI AND BS: USING THE QUANTILE REGRESSION METHOD

BÀNG B: LARGE BANK ACB, AGR, BID, CTG, EIB, HDB, MBB, SCB, SHB, STB, TCB, VCB, VIB, VPB (14 bank)												
	ROE				RAROA				Z-CORE			
	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90
ICT	-0.007	-0.024	-0.02**	-0.094*	0.003	-0.004	-0.006*	-0.029*	-2.69**	-3.14**	1.832	2.639
IT	0.169	0.100	-0.1851*	0.051	0.007	0.010	0.02**	-0.027**	-0.707	-2.17**	-1.994	-4.272
L_A	0.085	-0.092	-0.036	0.051	0.002	-0.005	-0.005	-0.011	-0.108	-1.020	-1.401	-5.96**
SIZE	0.004	0.028**	0.010	0.016	0.000	0.001	-0.001	0.000	0.176	0.115	0.261*	0.53**
ASSET_GRO	0.036	0.111*	0.101	0.171*	0.001	0.003	0.005	0.003	-0.895	-0.101	-0.514	-1.430
GDP_GRO	0.087	-0.427	-0.081	0.192	-0.025	-0.057	-0.048	0.063	-1.692	1.154	4.981	13.390
INF	-0.119	-0.130	-0.495	-0.281	-0.013	-0.011	-0.1***	-0.13**	-5.530	-7.88**	-9.853*	13.666
Cons	-0.146	-0.408	0.007	-0.134	0.010	0.001	0.040	0.004	-0.592	2.047	0.416	-1.594
No.obs	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154
Pseudo R2	0.127	0.126	0.113	0.092	0.041	0.041	0.094	0.220	0.084	0.089	0.095	0.123
BÀNG C: SMALL BANK ABB, BAB, BVB, KLB, MSB, NAB, OCB, PGB, PVB, SSB, VAB (11 bank)												
	ROE				RAROA				Z-CORE			
	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90	Q25	Q50	Q75	Q90
ICT	0.005	-0.029	-0.064	-0.169	-0.002	-0.005	-0.008	-0.0234*	0.594	-0.093	-0.976	-0.928
IT	0.050	0.0783	0.100	0.161*	0.006	0.0083*	0.007	0.0179*	-0.502	-0.685	-0.905	-0.497
L_A	0.132***	0.179***	0.185**	0.284*	0.007*	0.013***	0.014**	0.025***	-0.371	-0.749	-2.404**	-2.551
SIZE	0.022***	0.035***	0.033**	0.043*	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.003***	-0.190	-0.162	0.243	0.519*
ASSET_GRO	0.046	0.049	0.123	0.067	0.001	0.003	-0.001	0.002	-1.498**	-1.108	-1.492*	-0.412
GDP_GRO	-0.292	-0.145	-1.045*	-1.144*	-0.031	-0.047	-0.101	-0.214**	7.354	7.977	13.100	26.439*

INF	0.522**	0.471*	0.339	0.738* *	0.018	0.034	0.064**	0.090*	-6.338	-10.037	-13.26*	-12.099
Cons	-0.479	-0.721	-0.606	-0.778	-0.009	-0.016	-0.027	-0.052	7.174	7.978	2.663	-2.851
No.obs	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121
Pseudo R2	0.128	0.222	0.302	0.373	0.104	0.140	0.154	0.279	0.104	0.140	0.154	0.279

Note:: Q25, Q50, Q75 and Q90 are the 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th quantiles respectively. ***p < 0,01; **p < 0,05; * p < 0,1

Conclusion and policy implications

The study aiming to examine the impact of FI on BS distributions at different quantiles instead of only analyzing the impact at the mean value of BS as other studies have done before. This study found that FI negatively impacts BS in emerging markets such as Vietnam. Research reveals that fintech could bring instability to banks in emerging markets like Vietnam; Fintech has a negative impact on BS for large bank groups, while the relationship with small bank groups is unclear, possibly due to high management costs reducing their readiness to adopt technology. In addition, the study found that the trend and magnitude of FI's impact on BS also differ across different quantiles, with the negative impact of FI on BS becoming stronger in low-stability banking groups. Finally, bank-specific variables (financial structure, bank size, asset growth rate) have different levels and trends of impact on BS at different quantiles.

The study has several new contributions: *Firstly*, supplement the research results with experimental studies related to the relationship between FI and BS. *Secondly*, this research enriches the literature by analyzing the heterogeneity of fintech's level and trend at different percentiles of BS. *Thirdly*, this result provides detailed information for shareholders and bank managers in emerging countries on the cautious deployment of fintech to ensure sustainable financial development. They should also consider the ownership structure, bank capital size, and asset growth rate to further assess FI to BS, thereby having the right orientation policy. Due to time and scope limitations, the data were only collected in one emerging market over a short period of time and the FI measurement can be extended in many different ways. Future research directions can be expanded to cover more countries and regions to add more information about the impact trends of FI and BS in the banking industry.

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